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Research Article

ANALYSIS OF G6PD DEFICIENCY IN NEONATAL HYPERBILIRUBINEMIA

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Abstract:

Introduction: Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia (defined as a total serum bilirubin level exceeding 5 mg/dl) is a frequent problem as neonatal jaundice affects 65% of full-term infants and 85% of preterm infants after 24 h of life. **Objectives of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the G6PD (Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase) deficiency in neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. **Material and methods:** This descriptive study was conducted in Abbottabad International Medical Institute and Abbottabad Medical Complex from July 2019 till Feb 2020. This study was done with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. The data was collected from 197 patients. The age of selected patients was 0 day to 20 days. The data was collected through a survey method. Data about sex, gestational age, age at presentation, and length of hospitalization were collected for all patients. **Results:** The data was collected from 197 patients from which 61 female infants and 136 male infants. Patients with bilirubin levels between 10-30mg/dl were taken in this study. According to demographic data the maximum age in this study was 18 days and minimum age was new born. From 197 selected participants there were 176 were normal and 21 were G6PD deficient at neonatal age. There were 176 patients who had normal G6PD levels. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that G6PD deficiency is a common disease in infants. It is considered an important risk factor for severe hyperbilirubinemia.

Key words: Neonates, Deficiency, Hyperbilirubinemia

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INTRODUCTION:

Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia (defined as a total serum bilirubin level exceeding 5 mg/dl) is a frequent problem as neonatal jaundice affects 65% of full-term infants and 85% of preterm infants after 24 h of life. The most common clinical feature of G6PD deficiency is a lack of symptoms. However, in symptomatic neonates, the presenting features are neonatal jaundice and/or acute hemolytic anemia. Jaundice usually appears by age 1–4 days, at the same time as or slightly earlier than physiological jaundice [1,3].

The glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) enzyme is part of the pentose monophosphate shunt [1]. It catalyzes the oxidation of glucose-6-phosphate and the reduction of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate to nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH). NADPH maintains glutathione in its reduced form, which acts as a scavenger for dangerous oxidative metabolites. The erythrocytes do not generate NADPH in any other way; they are more susceptible than other cells to destruction from oxidative stress [2].

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency is the most common enzyme deficiency in humans, affecting 400 million people worldwide. It has a high prevalence in persons of African, Asian, and Mediterranean descent. It is inherited as an X-linked recessive disorder. G6PD deficiency is polymorphic, with more than 300 variants. G6PD deficiency confers partial protection against malaria, which probably accounts for the persistence and high frequency of the responsible genes [4].

G6PD deficiency is the most common red cell enzymopathy estimated to affect 400 million people worldwide. A recent systematic review showed a global prevalence of 4.9% for G6PD deficiency [2]. There is significant association of G6PD deficiency with neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in the immediate perinatal period. Though rare, significant

hyperbilirubinemia poses a potential threat for permanent neurological deficit or kernicterus [5]. Studies indicate that insufficient hepatic metabolism of unconjugated bilirubin rather than increased hemolysis is the major contributor to neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. In addition, the UGT1A1 mutation of promoter or coding region in *G6PD* contributes to a Gilbert like condition [6].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyse the G6PD (Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase) deficiency in neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in Abbottabad International Medical Institute and Abbottabad Medical Complex from July 2019 till Feb 2020. This study was done with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. The data was collected from 197 patients. The age of selected patients was new 0 days to 20 days. The data was collected through a survey method. Data about sex, gestational age, age at presentation, and length of hospitalization were collected for all patients. G6PD test was performed using fluorescence spot test (1 mL of whole blood in ethylenediamine tetra acetic acid tube). The standard value for bilirubin was 10-30mg/dl in our study.

The data was collected and analysed using Excel (2013).

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 197 patients from which 61 (30.96%) female infants and 136 (69.03%) male infants. Patients with bilirubin levels between 10-30mg/dl were taken in this study. According to demographic data the maximum age in this study was 18 days and minimum age was new born. From 197 selected participants there were 176 (89.34%) normal and 21 (10.6%) were G6DP deficient at neonatal age. There were 176 (89.345) patients who had normal G6PD levels. From 21 deficient patients there were 2 female (10%) and 19 males (90.47%).

Table 01: Data of 197 selected patients of present study

S.No	Age (days of life)	Sex	G6PD level normal= 1, deficient= 2
1	4	m	1
2	3	m	1
3	18	m	1
4	8	m	1
5	2	m	2
6	8	f	1
7	5	m	1
8	4	f	2

9	8	m	1
10	5	f	1
11	4	m	1
12	5	m	1
13	5	m	1
14	5	m	1
15	6	m	1
16	13	m	1
17	2	m	1
18	2	f	1
19	6	m	2
20	4	m	2
21	4	m	2
22	4	m	2
23	3	m	1
24	10	m	2
25	10	m	1
26	4	m	1
27	5	m	1
28	5	m	1
29	3	f	1
30	1	m	2
31	6	m	1
32	5	f	1
33	2	m	1
34	8	m	2
35	5	m	1
36	5	f	1
37	3	m	1
38	10	m	2
39	10	m	2
40	6	f	1
41	5	m	1
42	3	f	1
43	7	m	1
44	5	m	2
45	3	m	2
46	4	m	1
47	5	m	2
48	3	f	1
49	7	m	2
50	8	m	1
51	5	m	1
52	10	m	2

53	4	m	1
54	5	m	1
55	4	m	2
56	4	f	2
57	8	m	1
58	4	m	2
59	3	f	1
60	4	m	1
61	5	f	1
62	6	f	1
63	8	m	1
64	7	m	1
65	5	m	1
66	2	m	1
67	2	f	1
68	8	f	1
69	10	m	2
70	7	m	1
71	8	m	1
72	4	m	1
73	10	f	1
74	6	f	1
75	1	m	2
76	6	f	1
77	4	m	2
78	10	f	1
79	7	f	1
80	8	m	1
81	5	f	1
82	6	m	1
83	6	m	1
84	4	m	1
85	4	f	1
86	3	m	1
87	14	m	2
88	5	m	2
89	3	m	1
90	6	m	2
91	3	m	1
92	4	f	1
93	4	f	1
94	4	m	1
95	3	f	1
96	2	f	1

97	4	m	2
98	5 days	M	1
99	5 days	M	1
100	9 days	M	1
101	4 days	M	1
102	4 days	M	1
103	5 days	M	1
104	7 days	F	1
105	5 days	M	1
106	10 days	M	1
107	3 days	M	1
108	7 days	M	1
109	6 days	M	1
110	6 days	M	1
111	2 days	M	2
112	2 days	M	2
113	3 days	M	2
114	20 days	M	2
115	4 days	M	2
116	16 days	M	2
117	5 days	M	2
118	4 days	F	1
119	3 days	M	1
120	9 days	M I	1
121	9 days	M II	1
122	7 days	F	1
123	2 days	F	1
124	4 days	F	1
125	3 days	M	1
126	5 days	M	1
127	4 days	M	1
128	7 days	M	1
129	9 days	M	1
130	4 days	F	1
131	3 days	M	1
132	1 days	M	1
133	4 days	M	1
134	3 days	F	1
135	4 days	F	1
136	3 days	M	1
137	8 days	F	1
138	6 days	M	1
139	4 days	M	1
140	15 days	M	1

141	6 days	M	1
142	1 days	F	1
143	4 days	F	1
144	7 days	M	2
145	5 days	M I	2
146	5 days	M II	2
147	7 days	M	2
148	8 days	M	2
149	1 days	M	2
150	15 days	M	2
151	7 days	M	2
152	7 days	M	2
153	6 days	M	2
154	3 days	F	1
155	5 days	M	1
156	4 days	F	1
157	1 days	M	1
158	4 days	M	1
159	2 days	M	1
160	3 days	F	1
161	3 days	F	1
162	11 days	M	1
163	7 days	F	1
164	6 days	F	1
165	3 days	F	1
166	NB	M	1
167	8 days	F	1
168	5 days	M	1
169	3 days	M	1
170	10 days	F	1
171	5 days	M	1
172	5 days	F	1
173	3 days	M	1
174	3 days	M	1
175	5 days	M	1
176	7 days	M	1
177	3 days	F I	1
178	3 days	F II	1
179	3 days	M	1
180	1 days	F	1
181	4 days	F	1
182	5 days	M	1
183	3 days	F	1
184	6 days	F	1

185	4 days	M	1
186	4 days	F	1
187	4 days	M	1
188	6 days	M	1
189	7 days	F	1
190	1 days	F	1
191	3 days	F	1
192	6 days	M	1
193	4 days	M I	1
194	4 days	M II	1
195	2 days	F	1
196	3 days	M	1
197	3 days	F	1

DISCUSSION:

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency increases the vulnerability of erythrocytes to oxidative stress. Clinical presentations include acute hemolytic anemia, chronic hemolytic anemia, neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, and an absence of clinical symptoms. The disease is rarely fatal [7]. Several risk factors were identified in G6PD normal infants. The main risk factor for jaundice was identified as prematurity either with or without sepsis in G6PD normal infants. This finding corroborates previously published reports describing a high risk of bilirubin production-conjugation imbalance in borderline premature infants. Sepsis which is a leading cause of neonatal mortality in developing countries carries a high risk for jaundice in preterm infants in contrast to term infants [8].

G6PD is one of the antioxidant enzymes that protect the cell from injury. G6PD deficiency is estimated to affect 200 million individuals worldwide. It is more common in the Mediterranean area, Middle East, India, China, and Africa [9]. G6PD deficiency is an independent risk factor for high serum bilirubin level ≥ 18 mg/dL. It is considered as one of the most common clinically significant enzyme defects. G6PD-deficient individuals are usually healthy and asymptomatic but acute hemolysis may occur after ingestions of certain drugs, food, and exposure to certain chemicals, infections or hypoxia [10]. They could be attributable to the early onset hemolysis due to oxidative stress as a result of perinatal events. Chronic nonspherocytic hemolytic anemia may rarely occur [11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that G6PD deficiency is a common disease in infants. It is considered an important risk factor for severe hyperbilirubinemia. In infants with G6PD deficiency, management of

hyperbilirubinemia should be hastened to avoid irreversible neurological complications.

REFERENCES:

1. Koosha A, Rafizadeh B. Evaluation of neonatal indirect hyperbilirubinaemia at Zanjan Province of Iran in 2001-2003: prevalence of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency. *Singapore Med J*. 2007; 48:424–428.
2. Weng YH, Chiu YW. Clinical characteristics of G6PD deficiency in infants with marked hyperbilirubinemia. *J Pediatr Hematol Oncol*. 2010; 32:11–14.
3. Atay E, Bozaykut A, Ipek IO. Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency in neonatal indirect hyperbilirubinemia. *J Trop Pediatr*. 2006; 52:56–58.
4. Rice AC, Shapiro SM. A new animal model of hemolytic hyperbilirubinemia-induced bilirubin encephalopathy (kernicterus) *Pediatr Res*. 2008; 64:265–269.
5. American Academy of Pediatrics Subcommittee on Hyperbilirubinemia. Management of hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn infant 35 or more weeks of gestation. *Pediatrics*. 2004; 114:297–316.
6. Cappellini MD, Fiorelli G. Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency. *Lancet*. 2008; 371:64–74.
7. Al Arrayed S. Frequency of G6PD deficiency among Bahraini students: a ten years' study. *Bah Med Bull*. 2010; 32:18–21.
8. Ainoon O, Joyce J, Boo NY, Cheong SK, Zainal ZA, Hamidah NH. Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) variants in Malaysian Chinese. *Hum Mutat*. 1999; 14:352.
9. Agrawal SK, Kumar P, Rathi R, Sharma N, DAS R, Prasad R, et al. UGT1A1 gene polymorphisms in North Indian neonates presenting with unconjugated

- hyperbilirubinemia. *Pediatr Res.* 2009; 65:675–680.
10. Moiz B, Nasir A, Khan SA, Kherani SA, Qadir M. Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in infants with G6PD c.563C > T Variant. *BMC Pediatr.* 2012; 12:126.
 11. Samanta S, Kumar P, Kishore SS, Garewal G, Narang A. Donor blood glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency reduces the efficacy of exchange transfusion in neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. *Pediatrics.* 2009;123: e96–e100.